

Evaluation criteria for cancers in pregnancy

Deliverable 6.2. Recommendations

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Introduction

Non-invasive prenatal screening (NIPS) assesses the risk of foetal trisomies 13, 18, and 21 by analysing circulating cell-free DNA (cfDNA) in the maternal bloodstream¹. At 12 weeks of pregnancy, 5-15% of the cfDNA is derived from the placental trophoblasts, while the larger fraction is maternal²⁻⁴. Therefore, NIPS will not only identify CNVs arising from placental chromosomal anomalies but also any maternal chromosomal abnormalities which can be associated with constitutional imbalances or conditions such as maternal mosaicism, uterine myomas, or malignancies⁵⁻¹⁰.

Several studies have demonstrated the potential of NIPS to detect cfDNA derived from a tumour (circulating tumour DNA, ctDNA) and consequently diagnose incipient maternal malignancies^{5-8,11,12}. Occult maternal malignancies during NIPS have been identified in about 1 in 8000 to 10000 pregnancies¹³. However, the estimated occurrence of cancers during pregnancies is 1 in 1000 to 1500.

The lack of guidelines or recommendations on how to deal with those incidental findings often precludes early reporting and consequent treatment during pregnancy. We recommend the identification of malignancy suspicious NIPS profiles needs to be part of the standard operating procedure (SOP) for the interpretation of the test. In those recommendations we provide both technical criteria when to report potential cancers in pregnancy during NIPS reporting and provide a detailed clinical work-up program, which can be followed. We envision those recommendations to be of widespread use for NIPS laboratories. The early reporting will trigger treatments during pregnancy likely resulting in improved outcomes.

Executive summary

The identification of a malignancy-suspicious NIPS profile should prompt a multidisciplinary diagnostic evaluation of the pregnant woman. In an ideal scenario, clinical geneticists are involved to report the NIPS diagnostic outcome and the patient is referred to an expert oncology team with knowledge of cancers in pregnancy and/or a specialist following pregnancy complications, i.e. a Cancer in pregnancy (CIP) contact person.

First, an expert foetal ultrasound assessment in a tertiary obstetric unit must be performed with screening for aneuploidy markers and growth restriction. Invasive prenatal testing (such as amniocentesis) is performed to rule out foetal/placental abnormalities.

The presence of (multiple) genome-wide (sub)chromosomal gains and/or losses should initiate a work-up exploring the origin of the aneuploidies. The patient should undergo medical history assessment, clinical examination, peripheral blood testing, and medical imaging. This often include whole-body diffusion-weighted magnetic resonance imaging (WB-DWI/MRI). If

a potential cancer is identified, a discipline-specific oncologist should be consulted for the further diagnostic work-up and treatment strategy

When the NIPS profile shows only a single CNV, the diagnostic work up should include the analysis of maternal leukocytes using an orthogonal method. If this method is negative for this CNV, the diagnostic work-up should proceed to exclude the presence of a solid tumour. If the maternal leukocytes show the CNV, a complete blood count should be performed. In case of abnormal blood cell count, the patient should be referred to a haematologist for further investigations. If the blood count is normal, referral to a haematologist and a one-year follow-up could be considered upon explicit request by the patient or the requesting physician. An isolated trisomy 8 should always raise suspicion for a hematologic malignancy and referral to a haematologist is recommended.

Technical criteria for suspicion of malignancy

1. The presence of multiple genome-wide (sub)chromosomal gains and/or losses
2. Single trisomy or monosomy,
3. Maternal CNV overlapping with a gene from the list of cancer-related genes defined by the American College of Medical Genetics and Genomics (ACMG)¹⁴ or the CAN.HEAL data resources.

A single CNV suspected to indicate maternal malignancy: Perform an analysis to exclude the presence of chromosomal anomalies on maternal leukocytes detected in the NIPS sample. This can be fluorescent in situ hybridization (FISH), chromosomal microarrays or sequencing based analysis of the white blood cell DNA.

- **If negative:** start the clinical diagnostic work-up (see below) to rule out a solid tumor.
- **If positive:**
 1. **Review recent blood cell count.** If necessary, contact the treating gynecologist to access these results.
 - **Abnormal blood cell count:** refer to hematology for further work-up.
 - **Normal blood cell count:** likely no hematological malignancy. No further communication to the patient.*
 - **Blood cell count unavailable:** check the literature to determine whether the CNV is associated with hematological malignancies.
 - **If yes,** consider informing the patient for a new blood test including blood cell count.
 - **If no,** no further communication to the patient.*

If explicitly requested by the patient or referring physician: refer to hematology and schedule a follow-up consultation after one year. If results remain normal after one year, discontinue follow-up.

2. **Assess the degree of mosaicism:**

- **Low-grade mosaicism** ¹⁵⁻¹⁷: likely clonal hematopoiesis of indeterminate potential (CHIP). No amniocentesis needed.
- **High-grade mosaicism**: possible germline involvement. Perform an amniocentesis. Depending on the involved genes and phenotypic indications in the mother, conduct a clinical evaluation and, if necessary, examine a second maternal tissue sample.

Isolated trisomy 8 ¹⁸: Perform an analysis to exclude the presence of chromosomal anomalies on maternal leukocytes present in the NIPS sample.

- **If T8 is positive**: refer to hematology for further follow-up and diagnostics. No amniocentesis needed.
- **If T8 is negative**: likely of fetal or placental origin. Perform an amniocentesis:
 - **If T8 is positive**: likely fetal aneuploidy.
 - **If T8 is negative**: likely confined placental mosaicism (CPM).

In case of moderate suspicion with multiple dubious chromosomal aberrations: repeat NIPS on a new sample. If the result is again abnormal, start the clinical diagnostic work-up (see below).

In case of strong suspicion with multiple clear chromosomal aberrations: start the clinical diagnostic work-up (see below).

Clinical Diagnostic Work-Up

Patient Follow-up:

The clinical geneticist contacts the contact CIP contact person and the treating gynecologist. The clinical geneticist counsels the patient. The CIP contact person will coordinate and schedule further appointments. Additional diagnostics will include a comprehensive blood test, supplemented by a whole-body MRI and a biopsy. Depending on the results, a specialist oncologist will be consulted.

The CIP contact person will discuss the results with the patient, in consultation with the relevant disciplines, depending on the outcomes of further investigations. If malignancy is suspected or confirmed, a follow-up treatment pathway can be offered.

Screening for Fetal Abnormalities

- Advanced ultrasound with screening for aneuploidy markers and growth restriction.
 - Invasive genetic testing followed with an aneuploidy test. This can be karyotyping, chromosomal microarrays or massive parallel sequencing. Preferably amniocentesis samples are used.
 - If a chorionic villus sampling (CVS) has been performed, additional amniocentesis is required to definitively rule out fetal aneuploidy.
 - Counseling of these results is conducted by a clinical geneticist.
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Identification of Primary Tumor: Multidisciplinary Oncology Team

- Familial oncological history
- Personal medical history
- Oncological antecedents
- Results of population screening programs (e.g., cervical smear test, mammography)
- Possible causes for non-interpretable NIPT results: benign neoplasms (e.g., fibroids), active systemic diseases (e.g., SLE), use of low molecular weight heparine (LMWH), vitamin B12 deficiency
- Anamnesis and clinical examination:
 - Abdomen
 - Breast
 - Cardiopulmonary
 - Gynecological (cervix, pelvis)
 - Skin
 - Liver & spleen
 - Lymph node regions
 - PPA

- Thyroid
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Technical Investigations

Blood Tests:

- Hematological parameters: complete blood count, peripheral blood smear, LDH, electrophoresis
- Calcium, vitamin B12, liver and kidney function (ALT, GGT, bilirubin, creatinine)
- Consideration of tumor markers. Caution: CA 15.3, SCCA, CA 125, and AFP may show falsely elevated values. Inhibin B, AMH, CA 19-9, and CEA can be reliably used.

Imaging:

- Whole-body diffusion-weighted MRI
- BEO ultrasound if a fibroid is detected

Further targeted investigations will be guided by the above research results. If suspicious lesions are detected, a biopsy will be performed for pathological confirmation.

Treatment and Clinical Follow-Up

Treatment always depends on:

- Type and stage of the tumor
- Gestational age at the time of diagnosis

It must always be taken into account that:

- Complex medical, ethical, psychological, and religious factors play a role
- Care should be provided by a multidisciplinary team
- Oncological treatment must be equivalent to the standard treatment for non-pregnant patients
- Treatment options and their impact on pregnancy, maternal prognosis, and long-term prognosis for the child must be discussed with the patient and her partner
- In early pregnancies (before viability, < 24 weeks), in cases of poor maternal prognosis, the option of pregnancy termination should be discussed

If the decision is made to terminate the pregnancy:

- Multidisciplinary team/ad hoc ethics committee consultation
- Case management by the fetal medicine case manager
- Psychosocial support must be provided
- If hospitalization is required for any reason, all patients from a gestational age of 24 weeks onwards will, in principle, be admitted.

Obstetric Risks

- Pregnancy loss (miscarriage/TOP – termination of pregnancy)
- Congenital abnormalities in case of teratogenic exposure
- Preterm birth
- Intrauterine growth restriction
- Hematological toxicity in case of chemotherapy (for both mother and child – with risks of anemia, neutropenia, and thrombocytopenia)
- Admission to the neonatal intensive care unit
- Maternal death

Discipline-Specific Considerations

HIGH-RISK OBSTETRICS:

- **Outpatient setting:**
 - Monitoring disease progression, fetal growth, and structural assessment before interventions (diagnostics/treatment)
 - Ultrasound monitoring of growth, Doppler studies, fetal well-being, and cervical length before each chemotherapy administration
 - NIPS is inconclusive regarding fetal trisomy in cases of maternal cancer: discuss potential amniocentesis
 - Discussion of termination of pregnancy (TOP) if desired or necessary for optimal treatment in pregnancies <24 weeks
 - Planning delivery based on oncological treatment and fetal/maternal well-being (interval of 3 weeks after last chemotherapy session)
 - Consider Triaxis® and flu vaccination in case of immunomodulating therapy
 - Glucose Challenge Test at 24 weeks gestation: **Caution** regarding timing in the context of steroid use!
- **Delivery:**
 - Vaginal or cesarean delivery based on obstetric indication
 - Chemotherapy up to 35 weeks (in a 3-week cycle); maintain a 3-week interval between the last chemotherapy cycle and delivery due to:
 - Possible complications related to hematopoietic suppression (bleeding, infection, anemia) in both mother and newborn
 - Potential drug accumulation in the fetus

- Aim for term delivery (≥ 37 weeks), unless fetal-toxic therapy (targeted therapy, radiotherapy in the third trimester) is needed or maternal condition deteriorates
- Lung maturation if delivery < 34 weeks
- Magnesium sulfate if delivery < 31 weeks
- **Hospitalization for obstetric complications:**
 - Avoid delivery during periods of hematotoxicity after chemotherapy (lower threshold for tocolysis)
 - Consider LMWH
- **Hospitalization for oncological treatment/surgery/oncological complications/other:**
 - Discussion on active versus conservative management for issues arising at 24-26 weeks
 - CTG monitoring perioperatively (> 24 weeks)
 - Pre- and postoperative ultrasound
 - Tocolysis during surgery if uterine manipulation occurs
- **Postpartum:**
 - Postpartum follow-up at 6 weeks
 - Discussion of contraception
 - LMWH

NEONATOLOGY (NEO):

- **Outpatient setting/hospitalization:**
 - Counseling regarding the consequences of prematurity in cases of impending preterm birth
 - Discussion of neonatal feeding choices based on maternal treatment (breast milk, breastfeeding, formula) and documentation in the medical record to ensure a clear feeding plan at delivery
- **Postpartum:**
 - Monitoring of the newborn following exposure to cytotoxic therapy
 - Post-chemotherapy follow-up:
 - Hematological profile; kidney and liver function:
 - Establish baseline from umbilical cord blood
 - Venous blood test in the first week of life (during Guthrie test/bilirubin check)

- Echocardiogram <1 week postnatal
 - If exposed to platinum-based therapy: hearing follow-up during childhood
 - SGA (small for gestational age) neonates: neonatal follow-up
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ONCOLOGY (Primary Involved Disciplines):

- **Outpatient setting:**
 - Oncological treatment and follow-up
 - Chemotherapy between 14 and 35 weeks gestation based on a risk-benefit assessment; dosing based on current maternal weight
 - Surgery possible in any trimester
 - Radiotherapy: case-dependent (ensure fetal radiation exposure <50-100 mGy)
 - Preferred corticosteroids: Methylprednisolone/Hydrocortisone (Solu-Medrol IV or Medrol PO) is preferred over Dexamethasone/Betamethasone, as Medrol is significantly metabolized in the placenta and reaches the fetus to a much lesser extent. Dexamethasone/Betamethasone crosses the placenta more easily, and studies have shown that repeated administration during pregnancy is associated with an increased incidence of attention problems and cerebral palsy in children. (Animal studies have shown increased body weight, delayed development, and hormonal disruptions.)
 - Preferred anti-emetics:
 - Primperan® (10 mg, max 3x/day PO) or
 - Zofran® (Ondansetron 8 mg PO or IV, max 3x/day)
 - Ondansetron can be followed by two additional 8 mg IV or IM doses at 2-4 hour intervals, or as a continuous infusion of 1 mg/hour for 24 hours
 - No human studies exist for Akynzeo®; it may be considered if other anti-emetics are ineffective.
 - Clinical experience suggests fewer side effects in pregnancy, allowing for a lower dose of anti-emetics.
 - Due to an increased risk of thromboembolism: Consider prophylactic LMWH if multiple risk factors are present (obesity, pelvic surgery, immobilization, C-section) (NICE Guidelines)
 - Neupogen® and Neulasta® can be administered during pregnancy in dose-dense regimens.
- Hospitalization for oncological treatment/surgery/oncological complications/other:
 - Refer to general surgical procedures in pregnant women

- Postoperative LMWH
- Adequate pain management
- Perioperative monitoring: contact obstetrics
- Postpartum:
 - Discussion of further therapy and follow-up
 - Chemotherapy can be resumed from:
 - Day 2 after vaginal delivery
 - Day 5 after uncomplicated C-section

Medical Procedures by Trimester

Procedure	First Trimester (<14 weeks)	Second Trimester (14-28 weeks)	Third Trimester (28-42 weeks)
Surgery	Possible	Possible	Possible
Extra-abdominal radiotherapy (if fetal exposure <50-100 mGy)	Case-dependent	Case-dependent	Not possible
Pelvic radiotherapy	Not possible	Not possible	Not possible
Chemotherapy	Not possible	Possible	Possible
Targeted/hormonal therapy	Not possible	Not possible	Not possible

ANESTHESIA:

- **Outpatient setting:**
 - Inform patient about anesthesia and perioperative care during pregnancy and delivery
- **Hospitalization for oncological treatment/surgery/oncological complications/other:**
 - Refer to general surgical procedures in pregnant women
 - Postoperative LMWH
 - Adequate pain management
 - Perioperative monitoring: contact obstetrics

ONCO-PSYCHOLOGY:

- **Throughout the entire process:**
 - Assess impact of cancer diagnosis during pregnancy

- Referral to psychiatry if needed
 - Guidance on managing other children
 - Assess partner's needs
 - Social support: maternity benefits, maternity assistance, independent midwife, home care, etc.
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